

PR 103 yielded 86.7 kg/ha daily in trials at Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

energy in the shortest rice-growing period to give maximum yield per unit of area and per unit of time at a low cost. To identify such efficient type, 218 newly developed, short-statured cultures from various crosses were grown in a replicated yield trial at the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala. Data on duration in the field and on daily grain

production per hectare were recorded.

Daily grain production per hectare varied widely. Varieties with a growth duration of 80 to 140 days produced 25 kg to 90 kg/day per ha (Table 1). The varieties that performed well are compared with the present high yielding varieties of the Punjab in Table 2.

The varieties in group II of Table 2

show promise as replacements for almost all high yielding varieties of the Punjab; they may also help to prolong the transplanting period. They would also vacate the fields from 10 to 20 days earlier than the presently grown varieties and thus allow farmers to prepare the fields for timely sowing of wheat. The higher daily grain production per hectare of those varieties seems to represent a high physiological capacity to mobilize photosynthates and to translocate these to organs having economic value. A detailed study of the morphophysiological traits of these groups can provide better selection criteria for genetic gain in paddy yield improvement. A conspicuous morphological character of PR 103, which gave the highest daily grain yield of 86.7 kg/day per ha, seems to be its very long (60–80 cm) and upright flag leaf (see photo) that intercepts maximum sunlight during the grain-filling phase in the field. Hybridization programs may use such varieties widely to transfer their desirable traits to other varieties. **W**

Co 40 or Rajarajan — a new high yielding, long-duration monsoon rice

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The monsoon season in the Coromandal coastal belt and Cauvery basin of Tamil Nadu extends from August to December. The monsoon is characterized by factors not normally favorable for increased rice yields — cool temperature (from 25.1°C to 29.7°C), short duration of sunlight (from 5.5 to 8.3 hours/day), monsoon cloudiness, and high rain intensity (from 927 to 1,144 mm in 50–53 rainy days). Despite these unfavorable conditions, 60 to 70% of the rice area in India, particularly in Tamil Nadu (1.62 to 1.69 million ha), is grown to monsoon rice.

In spite of the development of several high yielding varieties, the specific varietal needs for the large monsoonal rice area, including high yield potential

and long growth duration, have not been met. Neither national nor international rice breeding organizations have devoted much effort to the development of rice varieties with growth duration of longer than 140 to 145 days. Varieties with a long vegetative phase and a maturation period of 160 days or more would commence flowering at the end of the monsoon. Panicle emergence would then coincide with bright, dry, cool weather and slowly increasing temperature during the postmonsoon period. Inherently photoperiod-sensitive varieties grown now are tall indicas that yield low, mainly because of poor nitrogen utilization and

susceptibility to lodging and blast *Pyricularia oryzae*. The latest tall indica variety made available for monsoon cultivation is Co 25, from the cross Co 4/ADT-10. Co 25 is resistant to *Pyricularia*, is photoperiod-sensitive, and has a growth duration of 165 to 180 days. But it gives low yields of 3 to 3.5 t/ha (see table), because it lodges even at the early growth stage.

To achieve those objectives, IR8 and Co 25 were crossed in 1969 at the Paddy Breeding Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore. A number of derivatives were selected and tested for yield in the

Mean yield of Co 40 Rajarajan rice in the monsoon season (Aug. to Jan.) in Pondicherry and Tamil Nadu regions, India.

Trials	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	1974	1975	1976	1977	
Rice research station	7.5	6.8	6.7	6.6	6.9
Adaptive trials in farmers' fields	—	5.6	6.1	6.0	5.9
Demonstration in farmers' fields	—	—	6.4	6.6	6.5
Mean	7.5	6.2	6.5	6.5	6.1
Local check (Co 25)	3.7	2.6	4.1	3.7	3.5

monsoon period. TNAU finally selected one such culture, TNAU 13493, and released it for cultivation in 1977 as Co 40 Rajarajan. This variety grows to 110 cm and matures in 165 to 170 days. Its grain is short and bold and the length:width ratio is 2.23. The vegetative period extends from 110 to 115 days.

Some significant characteristics of Rajarajan are 1) medium-tall stature with lodging resistance, 2) photoperiod sensitivity, 3) high photosynthetic ability even in cloudy monsoon weather,

4) resistance to *Pyricularia*, 5) high field tolerance for bacterial blight, 6) nitrogen utilization at moderate levels (80–120kg/ha), and 7) high yielding ability (from 6 to 7.5 t/ha vs 3 to 3.5 t/ha for the existing tall indica varieties) (see table).

Seedlings of Rajarajan can be planted after 50 to 60 days in the nursery beds so that its 110- to 115-day field duration is in the management limit of small farmers with available rainfall and a little stored water left in seasonal ponds during

postmonsoonal dry periods.

The yields of Rajarajan in research stations, adaptation trials in farmers' fields, and demonstration plots from 1974 to 1977 are given in the table. Other advantages are its yield stability across seasons and locations, and its medium-tall stature that makes it a source of rice straw, a stable feed for cattle in this region. Rajarajan is well received by the local farmers.

Fifteen participants in 1978 GEU training program

Fifteen participants from Bangladesh, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Thailand attended the 1978 Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) training program at IRRI from February 15 to June 16 (see photo). The course includes both instruction and practical experience in the basic skills essential to the operation of successful rice improvement programs, emphasizing and demonstrating the importance of multidisciplinary cooperation.

The GEU training program is basically skills oriented. Participants enhance their competence in screening to identify desirable rice characters, in combining such characters through selective plant

Participants in the 1978 GEU training program checking their hybridized plants in the IRRI plant breeding greenhouse. From left to right are: S. Ponnuthurai, D. L. Wichremasingha, and G. G. Saparamadu from Sri Lanka; M. Potisurintara, A. Thaotho from Thailand; I. Hadisjaban, A. Subardjo, A. Kartohardjono, Z. A. Simanullang, Sumarno, and A. E. Kosman from Indonesia; and M. B. Alam, Q. A. Haque, Md. A. Hossain, and P. K. S. Ray from Bangladesh.

breeding, and in evaluating the progeny. Candidates for GEU training are carefully selected. Only highly motivated

and active rice scientists of leadership potential with a knack for hard work qualify.

The diffusion of specific semidwarf rices as parents in Asian rice breeding programs over 10 years

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Although researchers have traced the spread of the improved rice varieties onto farmers' fields, little is known about their diffusion as parent varieties into breeding programs. Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews with rice breeders, the International Rice Research Institute studied changes in the rices used as parents in 355 randomly selected crosses made over a 10-year period at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations: Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Korea, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. The

research project was partially funded by a grant from The Rockefeller Foundation. The most popular single gene source in the 1965–67 sample of crosses was Taichung Native 1 (TN1), a semidwarf variety developed in Taiwan in 1956. TN1 was used in 22% of the total crosses, IR8 in 20%, and other IRRI lines in 14% (see figure, A).

By 1970, the use of TN1 had dropped sharply: by 1974–75 TN1 was used in only 1% of the crosses. The use of IR8 increased slightly by 1970–71, but dropped to only 3% by 1974–75. The use of IRRI varieties and lines other than IR8 as parents increased to about 44% of the crosses by 1974–75; the use of semidwarfs introduced from other countries also increased slightly.

But the strongest trend was the growing use of *locally developed*

A. Use of semidwarf parents in the rice breeding programs of 7 Asian nations over a 10-year period. Eight hundred and nineteen parents used in 355 randomly selected crosses at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities.